

USE OF SPEECH STYLE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK WRITTEN TEXTS

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Annotation. This article is devoted to the investigation of speech styles which provide information about speech styles, types of styles and specific features of styles in English and Uzbek.

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There are written and spoken forms of literary language. Both forms of speech rely on literary language. However, there are no punctuation, spelling standards, pronunciation standards, and intonation standards that apply to written speech. Therefore, in the field of speech culture there are concepts such as written speech culture and oral speech culture. The scope of written speech includes scientific speech, official speech, journalistic speech in part, literary speech, as well as the language of written texts prepared for radio and television.

The scientific method, which is the subject of scientific research for linguists, is a set of specific speech techniques used primarily in the field of scientific, scientific, technical and popular science, to express various ideas, hypotheses and achievements in content and purpose, and used to form. A scientific text is the result or outcome of a research activity created for a group of people who are appropriately qualified to perceive and evaluate. To make it as informative as possible, the author should use written language, special tools and methods of presenting the material. Often, a scientific text is a work that is published or intended for publication. The texts of the scientific plan include materials specially prepared for oral presentation, for example, a report of a conference or an academic lecture.

The characteristic features of the scientific method are the tone, objective approach and disorganization of information, the structure of the text, the availability of terminology, and the means of special languages adopted for the logical and adequate presentation of materials among scientists¹.

¹ Nurmonov A., M a h m u d o v N., Ahmedov A., S o l i x o ' j a y e v a S. O'zbek tilining mazmuniy sintaksisi. - Toshkent: Fan, 1992. - B. 28-30;

The spread of the written form of works in the scientific style is determined by the authenticity, situation, accuracy of their content and design. The distribution of scientific texts by types and types is explained, first of all, by the differences in the described objects from many disciplines, the content of the research activities of scientists, and the perspectives of the potential audience. There are main features of scientific literature that divide texts into scientific-technical, scientific, humanitarian, scientific and natural aspects. Algebra, Botany, Political Science, etc. It is possible to distinguish individual sub-entries that exist in each of the disciplines.

M.P. Senkevich compiled the types of scientific methods at the level of the "scientific character" of the final product and distinguished the following types:

1. In fact, scientific methods (otherwise - academic) are intended for a narrow range of specialists and are typical for serious works that include the concept of author monographs, articles and scientific lectures.
2. The presentation or generalization of the scientific heritage includes secondary information materials (theses, comments) - they are created in a scientific-educational or scientific-summary style.
3. There are new advances in technology, electronics, chemistry, pharmacology, and other advanced science fields in industrial advertising that reflect the results and advantages of specific products in certain advertising and scientific fields.
4. Scientific literature (books, collections, dictionaries, catalogs) provides information to students so that they do not give too specific, precise, detailed information.
5. A special field used in educational and scientific literature, where subject bases are created and didactic components are added to provide repetitive elements and materials (educational literature for various educational institutions).
6. Popular scientific literature presents the biography of famous people, the history of the origin of various phenomena, the chronicle of events and discoveries, and is open to many interested persons through illustrations, examples, and explanations.

A text created in scientific style is a standardized closed system. The main features of the scientific method are compliance with the normative requirements of the literary language, the use of standard sequences and expressions, the use of the possibilities of the language of "symbolic" symbols and formulas, the use of zikr and notes. For example, clients are generally

accepted in the scientific community: for example, ... it should be noted that the data obtained during the study led to the following conclusions ... let's proceed to the analysis ... and so on.

To transfer scientific information to "artificial" language elements: 1) graphics, circles, blocks, drawings, drawings are widely used; 2) formulas and symbols; 3) special terms and lexical features of the scientific method, for example, names of physical quantities, mathematical symbols, etc.

Reference devices (footnotes, comments, notes) form more specific ideas about the topic of speech and serve to implement the quality of scientific speech, such as the accuracy of terms and the verification of sources.

That is, scientific methods, characterized by conformity to the norms of literary language, serve accuracy, precision and laconicism in the expression of research ideas. A monologic form is characteristic for a scientific lecture, the logic of the statement is consistently determined, the conclusions are formalized in the form of a complete and clear expression².

Each text of the scientific method has its own logic of construction, which has a specific form that corresponds to the laws of construction. Usually the researcher follows the following scheme:

- Introduction to the essence of the problem, its relevance and renewal;
- Choosing a research topic (in some cases, an object);
- Setting goals, solving certain tasks during performance;
- Review of scientific sources that affect the research topic in any way, description of the theoretical and methodological basis for the work; Basis of terms;
- Theoretical and practical importance of scientific work;
- Content of scientific work;
- Description of the experiment, if it is carried out;
- Research results, conclusions based on its results.

Abstract tone and generalization form the lexical features of the scientific method:

1. The use of words in specific meanings, the superiority of words in an abstract sense (size, clarity, resistance, conflict, stagnation, word formation, bibliography, etc.).

² Muhiddinova X, Salisheva Z, Po'latova X. O`zbek tili (oliy ta'lim muassasalari rus guruhlari uchun darslik). – Toshkent: O`qituvchi, 2012. – 288

2. Words in everyday life have a terminological or general meaning within the scope of scientific work. This is used, for example, for technical terms: clutch, tape, pipe, etc.

3. The main semantic load in a scientific text is filled with terms, but their share is not the same in different types of works. Translation terms embody specific concepts, correct and logical definition is a necessary condition for a professionally written text (ethnogenesis, genome, sinusoid).

4. Typical examples of scientific methods, abbreviations and complex words: publishing house, GOST, Gosplan, million, scientific research institute.

Linguistic features of the scientific method, in particular, have functional directions in the field of vocabulary: the generalized abstraction of the presentation of the material, the behavior and conclusions of the author, the accuracy of the presented information.

Morphological features of the scientific method:

At the level of grammar, the abstraction of a scientific text is created by establishing specific word forms and word combinations and sentences: this ... and so on.

2. Verbs in the context of a scientific text have an eternal, generalized meaning. And mostly present and past forms are used. Their exchange is not "imagery" or the dynamics of the narrative, on the contrary, they indicate the regularity of the phenomenon described: the author states, ...; Solving problems, etc., will help you achieve this goal.

3. Verbs of not less types (about 80%) also have the generalized meaning of the scientific text. Verbs of the perfect type are used in stable circles: think ...; We are examples, etc. In addition, non-traditional personal and inappropriate forms of necessity or obligation are used with a shadow: features ...; You should know that ...; Don't forget...

4. Reflexive verbs are used in the passive sense: it should be proved ...; Described in detail ...; The forms of such verbs make it possible to emphasize the definition, structure, mechanism of the process. The same meaning for short passive participles: it is given a limit ...; The norm can be understood, etc.

5. Scientific speech also uses short adjectives, for example: attitude is characteristic.

6. A typical sign of scientific speech is the status used instead of I. This method forms features such as simplicity, objectivity, generality of authorship: during the study we came to the conclusion ... (instead I came to the conclusion ...).

The linguistic features of the scientific method from the point of view of syntax show that the speech depends on the scientist's own thinking: the constructions used in the texts are neutral and commonly used. The most typical is the method of syntactic compression, when the size of the text increases the information and semantic content. This is done using special sentences and sentences of word combinations.

Syntactic features of the scientific method:

1. The use of expressions in which the term "noun + noun in relevant terms" is used: metabolism, currency liquidity, dismantling device, etc.
2. Terms expressed by adjectives are used in the meaning of the term: unconditional reflex, rigid sign, historical excavation, etc.
3. For scientific methods (definitions, foundations, conclusions) a composite nominal predicate with a name is characteristic, usually expressed by a verb-lingament: feelings are the main knowledge process ...; Deviation from the normative implementation of language is one of the most striking features of a child's speech. Another common "predetate formula" is a nominal predicate attached to a short number: it can be used.
4. Adverbs for the role of situations serve to describe the quality or nature of the phenomenon under investigation: significant, interesting, reliable, in a new way; These and other events are well described in historical literature.
5. The syntactic structures of words represent the conceptual content, so the standard of the writing scientist is that the type of the word belongs to the sentence of complete sentences, the union relationship between its parts, neutrality in terms of methodology and neutrality with the normative order of the word. Ladi: The most developed anthropoid (chimpanzee) vocal language, which zoopsychologists have long, rigorously and unsuccessfully tried to teach. Among complex sentences, one subordinate structure prevails: between mind and language there is an intermediate basic communicative system called the functional basis of speech.
6. The importance of question sentences is to draw attention to the material presented, to express assumptions and hypotheses. Maybe a monkey could have sign language?
7. In order to present information deliberately and indirectly, suggestions of non-various individuals are widely used: the status of fair genres includes friendly communication (talking about spirits, chatting, etc.). Thus, the desire to be an objective researcher speaking on behalf of the generalized scientific community.

8. To formalize cause-effect relationships between phenomena, scientific speech uses complex sentences with combined and subordinate association relations. Often there are complex associations and allied words: nevertheless, although others are common, subordinate explanation, certainty, causes, conditions, time, effect.

The scientific method is based not only on the normative basis of language, but also on logical laws. Thus, researchers should use syntactic possibilities to logically express their thoughts, to connect morphological features of the scientific method and some parts of words. This purpose is served by various syntactic structures, various types of complex sentences with "clip-words", participation, participation, sorting, etc.

The main ones are:

- Comparison of any event (for example, ..., therefore ...);
- Use sentences containing additional information about what is said in the main part;
- Adverbial tournaments also contain additional scientific information;
- Introduction words and phrases, plug-in constructions serve for communication between semantic parts between sentences and paragraphs;
- "Clip-words" (for example, therefore, at the same time, at the end, in other words, as we see) serve to establish a logical connection between different parts of the text;
- Homogeneous members of the sentence are logically necessary to enumerate such concepts;
- Use of accelerated structures, logic and brevity of the syntactic system.

Thus, the scientific method of the means of communication that we have considered is a stable system whose characteristics are difficult to change. Despite the comprehensive system of scientific creativity, regulated norms help to "preserve form" in the scientific form.

In popular scientific literature, the presentation of material is neutral, close to general literature, as the reader is provided only with specially selected facts, interesting aspects, parts of historical reconstruction. The form of presentation of such information should be open to non-specialists, therefore, the selection of materials, the system of proofs and examples, the style of presenting information, the language and methods associated with popular scientific literature are slightly different from the actual scientific text.

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